

CURRICULUM INTEGRATION IN CHEMICAL ENGINEERING USING CDIO: CASE STUDY

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Abstract

This paper is Part Two of a 2-part submission to ISATE2013. It covers a specific example of curriculum integration using an “integrative” core module, Process Instrumentation and Control (PI&C), to facilitate integration of the chemical engineering curriculum in addition to the existing traditional approaches of using capstone Year 3 Plant Design and Final Year Projects. It firstly presents the challenges of teaching the module in the traditional chemical engineering curriculum, followed by presenting our experience in redesigning two real-world learning tasks that integrate across modules, CDIO skills and within domain knowledge areas from multiple disciplines. Secondly, it outlines the purpose in the redesigning of the learning activities to achieve an integrative experience. In the first redesigned activity, students assumed the roles of a newly promoted chemical engineer and process technicians to perform an online controller tuning task which was left uncompleted by the engineer’s predecessor who had since left the company. In the second redesigned activity, students assumed the roles of a team of polytechnic interns tasked to reinstate an old pilot plant training unit, connect the unit to a newly purchased Distributed Control System (DCS) followed by tuning a controller from the DCS. Feedback was gathered from students via oral interviews and focused group discussions and the findings from our evaluation are summarized and certain challenges identified. The paper concludes with a reflection on CDIO teaching experiences by the first author, who is relatively new to the teaching profession, as well as some recommendations for future action and improvement. Overall, the study yielded encouraging results; apart from an improvement in the semestral examination results, students found the learning experience interesting and meaningful. From their responses, it appeared that the enhanced learning experience can be attributed at least in part to good activity structuring and careful crafting of the questions to integrate process instrument and control concepts across various disciplines within and beyond chemical engineering.

Keywords: *CDIO, Curriculum integration, chemical engineering, process instrumentation and control*

Introduction

Process Instrumentation and Control (PI&C) is a Year 3 module in DCHE that has always been commonly regarded by students as a challenging and difficult subject in DCHE with abstract concepts which are difficult to comprehend and apply into real life situations. The “traditional” approach is for students to apply the process control principles in a “capstone” process *Plant Design Project* (PDP), mentioned in the previous section.

Challenges in Teaching Process Control

Due to the uniqueness of chemical processes, Bequette (2001) highlighted that teachings of process control differs significantly from that of electrical or mechanical engineers. In fact, Silverstein (2005) noted that process control has often stood out in the chemical engineering curriculum as a necessary topic that is oddly disconnected from the rest of the curriculum. This is especially true of its mathematical focus on process descriptions in the Laplace domain; which has made it appear to students as a course distinct from “regular” chemical engineering.

In reality, process control is key to industrial practice and will draw upon an engineer’s theoretical knowledge and practical experience to be effective. Seborg (2003) predicted that the scope and importance of process control technology will continue to expand during the 21st century. King (2011) noted that: “... revising the way that we teach process control to chemical engineers is becoming increasingly important. Too many are graduating with little knowledge relevant to the process industry and most leave university with the view that it is a highly mathematical subject understood by few.” Others like Clough (1998) and Moor (2004) called for different approaches like active learning or inductive learning respectively to teach the subject.

As an “integrative” module mentioned by Edgar (2006), the re-designed activities now connect directly

to the relevance of various topics in chemical engineering. Through curriculum integration, students will be able to find greater meaning and relevance in the modules learnt prior to PI&C and apply their prior knowledge learnt from other modules (and vice versa) to solve real life engineering problems instead of merely learning about control theories and algorithms. This will enhance the students' learning experience in both PI&C and chemical engineering as a whole.

For our initial effort, we revised two out of the existing five laboratory activities for the PI&C module. We used the student-centered Triangle of Course Design by Felder (2003) as shown in Figure 1 to ensure that the re-designed learning tasks and its assessment system are aligned to the desired learning outcome for curriculum integration.

Figure 1. Student-centered Approach to Curriculum Design

We used the tried-and-tested approach in DCHE for re-designing student learning activities by Cheah (2009), namely creating a real-world scenario for future work as a chemical engineer, who has to work in teams to solve simulated work problems requiring one to use knowledge in process control and other technical domains. Scenarios are used Collaborative learning is promoted through pre-activity assessment that ascertain students' preparedness for the activity, utilising a series of structured questioning in which each team member must contribute collectively to the overall group marks.

Discussion of work done

Case Study One

A newly promoted Chemical Engineer was approached by his Plant Manager to urgently complete the task of tuning a new level controller of a wastewater treatment tank which was supposed to be done by his predecessor who had since left the company. With a team of process technicians assigned to assist him with the task, the team had to complete an originally five – six hour task within three hours.

In this task, students were required to recall their technical knowledge on control theory, control algorithm and online controller techniques (in this case, the open loop step response technique using Ziegler-Nichols correlation is adopted) to design a suitable level controller based on appropriate control algorithm (P, I, D) and controller tuning parameter value (proportional band, integral time, derivative time). In order to perform the online controller tuning, students need to perform process line up, control valve stroke checking and finally starting up the unit in cold circulation using a suitable and safe substitute (which is water). After the open loop step response test is conducted, students collected an incomplete set of data (in view of serious time constraints) which they then had to extrapolate, predict and use the available information to determine the appropriate controller tuning parameter value. They then implemented the calculated controller tuning parameter value; test the response in automatic mode, and finally fine tune to obtain the optimum value by trial and error.

This activity supported the desired learning outcomes which capstone projects like plant design and final year projects could not consistently provide. Firstly, students were able to really operate what they designed. Unlike typical PDPs which students generally were only required to determine the appropriate control algorithm and calculate the corresponding controller tuning parameter value from simulation results or tedious mathematical calculations (more often, this was only done for a selected section of the designed plant), this activity moved one step forward to allow students to integrate C-D-I-O skills, and more importantly evaluate the effectiveness of their work and finally to obtain an optimized result. The physical hands-on in unit start up, operation and shut down is also something that they were able to experience, unlike in the case of PDP which is purely software simulation.

Secondly, by using a real-world scenario that requires engineers to handle urgent tasks within tight timelines, important CDIO skills were introduced. Students had to apply teamwork, communication and time management skills to complete the tasks within the time constraints. This could only be possible through proper planning and effective division of labor to bring out the synergy within the team.

Thirdly, students were given opportunity to evaluate the limitations in their initial design. The partial information obtained introduced elements of uncertainty which increases the challenges students faced to complete the task on time. They thus need to recognize possible sources of error and imperfections of the methods used; and understand that one cannot obtain the optimum result simply from the calculations alone. This gives them confidence to tackle problems, practice engineering judgment, manage uncertainty and incomplete information; all of which are inevitable in real-world engineering.

Fourthly, students were also being challenged at higher thinking levels when they were required to perform process troubleshooting based on the Five Steps of Process Troubleshooting technique proposed by Thomas (2009). Process fault scenarios were introduced whereby students are required to recognize the symptoms, hypothesize the cause of process faults, and propose actions and tests required to confirm their hypothesis.

Lastly, since this experiment involves the operation and control of a live process, the safety, health and environment aspects of plant operations were also being emphasized. Students were required to recognize and explain the various layers of protection in preventing the wastewater treatment tank from overflowing. In addition, students were also introduced to the concept of using a *safer substitute to minimize risk*. In the scenario, the wastewater treatment tank involves a neutralization process between a hazardous acid and alkali. Water was used as a suitable substitute in view of its non-hazardous nature and similar physical properties as compared to the acid and alkali mixture.

Case Study Two

A team of polytechnic students undergoing an industrial training programme has been tasked to reinstate an old pilot plant training unit which is used for training in PI&C. A new Distributed Control System (DCS) was purchased as part of this reinstatement, and students were required to connect the training unit to the DCS, commission the process unit and perform online controller tuning of the level controller using the heuristics method. Four different combinations of control algorithm and controller tuning parameter values were provided and students had to select the most suitable combination based on defined tuning objectives.

This activity supported the desired learning outcomes which industrial training programmes and capstone projects like plant design and final year projects could not consistently provide. Firstly, the common techniques of DCS operations were imparted to the students, and they got to experience real time operations under supervision without having to fear of upsetting an industrial process or creating unsafe conditions causing a plant to make off-spec products and hence potentially losing millions of dollars of revenue (that is the reason why most students undergoing industrial attachment or training in commercial plants never have the chance to even go near the control system!). Students were also given the opportunity to perform wiring connections to link the DCS with the pilot training unit; even though this work is commonly by instrumentation engineers in chemical plants, the techniques for performing such connections were easily related to the PMCC (Process-Measurement-Control-Correct) cycle which chemical engineers are familiar with.

Secondly, as this process involves operating a centrifugal pump, students need to recall their prior knowledge in rotating equipment to physically operate the pump in accordance with safe operating procedures. This is something that is lacking in PDPs. In simulation software, a pump is commonly just being understood by students as an equipment that is simply used to move liquid, but in real plant operations context, a pump means much more than just moving a liquid from one point to another. It takes understanding of the fundamentals of fluid mechanics, rotating equipment and plant safety in order to design a pump that is suitable in sizing, type (i.e. positive displacement or centrifugal) with instrumentation, control and safeguarding systems incorporated to ensure safe and optimum pump operations.

Thirdly, students were required to do a proposal evaluation. The scenario is that the reinstated pilot unit will be utilized to pump flammable hydrocarbons instead of water, hence the unit design needs to be modified and five modifications were proposed. Among them include:

- converting the column to a closed column.
- converting electrical instruments to pneumatic.
- designing a split range pressure controller for the column.
- designing a pressure relief system for the column.
- replacing the existing centrifugal pump.

Some of the proposals were appropriate while the others were not. Students then need to evaluate with explanation which are the ones that are appropriate and vice versa. This aspect of critical thinking is somewhat difficult to achieve when doing plant design as often the PDP merely require students to design the process flow diagram using steady state simulation mode without having to consider much on the specific equipment, safety and process control requirements.

Fourthly, to build on the scenario that the unit was to be used to pump flammable hydrocarbons, students were tasked to perform a Layer Of Protection Analysis (LOPA) to reduce the risk of a fire breakout for the newly proposed unit. The LOPA served as a good platform to supplement curriculum integration, given the nature that LOPA require students to apply concepts across multiple disciplines in chemical engineering; The coverage of LOPA components like critical alarms, safety instrumented functions, physical protection and emergency response are however usually limited in PDP, even though these are important competencies of chemical engineers demanded by the industry.

Evaluation: Issues and Challenges

We carried out focus group discussions with selected students to first find out if PDP and FYP adequately helped them integrate knowledge gained over their

course of study. We also wanted to know if the re-designed activities enhanced their understanding of their future job role as a chemical engineer. We also used a Reflection Journal (to be submitted individually) as a mean to evaluate if students are able to integrate the various technical and soft skills in the activities.

Confirming our expectation, students agreed that whether or not FYP is effective as an integrative capstone depends largely on the scope of each individual project. As for PDP, even though it was commonly agreed that it is a critical integrative capstone, many felt that there was too much emphasis on using the simulation software and insufficient guidance provided in seeing integrative links across modules. All students agreed that they were guilty of placing their emphasis of the project to get their simulations to converge by trial and error instead. They also admitted that integration efforts introduced in laboratory activities, notably written report assessment, are often circumvented by splitting up the work and complete their own sections of the report in silos; and that curriculum integration is still best achieved with actual plant experience.

From the focus group discussion, we identified three major challenges. The first challenge concerned the lack of guidance provided to them when performing the lab activities, which may have limited the effectiveness of achieving the intended integrative outcomes. Having been students ourselves, we acknowledge that at pre-employment level the students' plant experience is limited – hence expecting them to visualize a process plant at macro-level; linking problems and formulate solutions across multi-disciplines of chemical engineering is extremely challenging. To help overcome this challenge, it is inevitable that lecturers facilitating the lab activities might need to provide students with some guidance, especially when it comes to more open-ended problem solving. However, as lecturers, we have to be mindful that providing guidance does not mean providing students with solutions to the problems; rather it is about encouraging their thinking and activating prior knowledge that they could possibly make connections with. The quality of their solutions generally showed improvement, and students also agreed that the guidance provided did help them better comprehend the problem and coupled with the guidance provided by lecturers, they could solve the given problems with greater ease.

The second challenge is how to provide students with real plant operations experience at laboratory level. We agreed with the students' viewpoint that curriculum integration is best achieved through actual plant experience. On the other hand, we also acknowledged that whether students are able to gain the relevant plant experience during industrial training programs to allow curriculum integration largely depends on the company they have been posted to and the job scope assigned to them. Luckier students who were posted to the oil and

gas or petrochemical plants might stand a higher chance to perform job functions which allow them to practice what they had learnt in the chemical engineering curriculum, while a significant number of students might be assigned to more administrative roles which have limited room for them to put into practice knowledge and skills learnt in campus.

The third challenge identified is how to avoid students from working in silos when working on the practical activities. Students commonly agreed that one obstacle for curriculum integration using activities is that they have the tendency to apply "teamwork" by distributing the work to complete the tasks and assignments among the team mates. As a result, students have the tendency just to focus on the areas which they have been assigned to, complete their portion of their assignment and submit it to a team mate who does the overall compilation of the report. The completion of their respective portions were usually done with little consideration on how the different sections of the report could be interlinked and how solutions to an earlier problem could be applied to solve subsequent ones. Students generally agreed that it is being optimistic to say that one student from a group who puts in effort to compile the lab assignment at the very end would read and comprehend the submissions of their team mates, and edit the submission to make the entire submission cohesive and fluent. This is because on most occasions, students who compile individual contributions have the tendency to just "cut and paste" all different sections together for submission.

From the Reflective Journals submitted by the students, we obtained varied responses. On one hand, there are some students who reported focusing too much on the PI&C concepts and faced difficulties trying to interlink and integrate the different concepts across the curriculum into the task while, on the other hand, there are others who do not face such challenges. Using a Reflective Journal is a relatively new experience for us, and we need to improve its usage to be able to capture key aspects of the learning process and subsequently make better inferences and interpretations from the response data.

Overall, the results obtained were encouraging. Student feedback supported 'hands-on' work opportunities in helping them to apply knowledge and skills learnt in an operational level beyond just a paper exercise, and that is what the PDP cannot achieve. Students feedback highlighted the importance of good activity structuring in which the learning experience was made more interesting and meaningful; i.e. before the commencement of practical work, students were required to answer a set of pre-experimental assessment questions, which were crafted in such a way that they are task specific questions (rather than questions for which the answers can be directly retrieved from lecture notes) to help them understand the scenario better and why the task was performed in a particular manner or

sequence. Questions were also posed to them during the experiment which served as learning “check-points” to verify students’ understanding of the activity and its related concepts during the course of performing the experiment itself. Lastly, post-experiment and report assessment questions were introduced to help students consolidate the critical learning points; and, more importantly, how PI&C concepts learnt in the activity can be integrated and linked to different subject areas within and beyond chemical engineering. In conclusion, the re-designed activities allowed students to apply and practice C-D-I-O skills to design and formulate their solution to the problem, implement and optimize it and, as a result, better retain the knowledge and skills learnt. This is supported by better performance during the semestral examination.

Reflection of CDIO Pedagogical Experience (First Author) and Recommendations for Future Work

The CDIO pedagogy was something new to me until I joined SP as a DCHE Lecturer. I belong to the typical group of chemical engineering students who completed my laboratory activities, plant design and final year projects without much excitement that I had learnt new knowledge and skills that will benefit me as a future chemical engineer. It was only after I began employment in the chemical industry that I started to find meaning in what I had studied. I touched and operated live size rotating equipment, furnace, distillation columns, heat exchangers, and DCS for the first time in my life, and I finally understood the process, health and safety considerations behind the design and operation of each plant equipment and process which I could relate to my academic experience.

I was fortunate to be given the opportunity to design and conduct competency based training programs for prospective and in-employment chemical engineers and process technicians as I build up my working experience. Because I do not wish to see my students following my learning footsteps as a typical chemical engineering student, I believed that learners must be able to understand the reason behind every action they perform, and learning is best achieved through active experimentation, and allowing room to make mistakes. Based on my work experiences, I was familiar with the concept of active learning, but not CDIO. It was after my first rigorous exposure to CDIO through the redesigning and implementation of the activities for PI&C that I began to realize that CDIO is more than another curriculum framework. It provides a holistic approach to design a meaningful learning experience for students; that requires them to draw upon their prior knowledge of various knowledge bases, applying them to formulate a solution to a task, implementing the solution they had formulated, reviewing the effectiveness of their implemented solutions and making improvisations to refine their solution. In short, I am able to design an integrated learning experience “the

CDIO way” that allows students to learn in a more holistic and real world manner.

Several areas have been identified for improvement to achieve further curriculum integration. One possible area is the use of concept maps developed by Perkins (1991) to assess the achievement of the intended outcomes in an integrated curriculum. In the past twenty years, concepts map have been used to teach and assess conceptual understanding in mathematics and science education. Now these tools are being applied to humanities and social sciences, and to some extent in engineering education. We recognize that this practice had not been employed in our curriculum; and both faculty and students need to be adequately trained on how to draw concept maps in order for it to be a fair and valid assessment.

The remaining practicals in PI&C also offer opportunities to further strengthen the integration effort. We intend to purchase integrated pilot plants with the control of multiple equipment (e.g., tanks, pumps, reactors, etc), process parameters (flow, level, temperature, etc), redundancies and safety instrumented systems. I envision the improved PI&C practical sessions to firstly allow students to better apply systems thinking techniques in the plant operation and control because they will be able to better visualize how deviation in one process parameter can affect other downstream process parameters. For example, when a storage tank containing feed to a distillation column reaches a low level, it will cause the feed pump to trip. Students need to analyze how this loss of feed to the column is going to impact the liquid level, temperature and hence product distribution in the column. They will then need to take prompt actions to prevent the problem from worsening and restore the process to its safe condition; knowing that failure to do so will result in activation of the safety instrumented systems.

Encouraged by the positive outcome obtained so far, I look forward to revamp the remaining activities within the module along with the introduction of new integrated process units. However, I am also mindful that at the same time, while I intend to further implement curriculum integration to supplement capstone projects, the learning of PI&C should still be the primary focus, in view that knowledge and skills in the module will still likely remain an important aspect of chemical engineering. It is through accurate and timely process instrumentation and control that provides a process with maximum throughput, minimum downtime and waste generation and these humbly contributes towards sustainable development.

Conclusion

We had successfully completed a trial run of our integration curriculum using PI&C. Preliminary results from students’ learning experience indicate that they enjoyed the sessions and found studying the subject

more interesting and meaningful and this was supported by the improvement of students' results in the semestral examination. We will make use of the learning points identified above to continue to revise the remaining activities and improve on the module using CDIO.

References

- Cheah, S.M. and Koh, H.W. (2013). Curriculum Integration in Chemical Engineering using CDIO: General Approach, paper prepared for the International Symposium on Advances in Technology Education; September 25-27; Nara, Japan
- Bequette, W. and Ogunnaike, B.A (2001). Chemical Process Control Education and Practice, *IEEE Control Systems Magazine*, April 2001, pp.10-17
- Silverstein, D.L (2005). An Experiential and Inductively Structured Process Control Course in Chemical Engineering, *Proceedings of the 2005 American Society for Engineering Education Annual Conference & Exposition*
- Seborg, D.E., Edgar, T.F. and Mellichamp, D.A (2003). Teaching Process Control in the 21st Century: What has Changed?, *Proceedings of the 2003 American Control Conference*, June 4-6, 2003; Denver, Colorado, USA
- King, M (2011). Turned off by Teaching, *TCE Magazine*, April 2011, pp.52-54.
- Clough, D.E (1998). Bringing Active Learning into the Traditional Classroom: Teaching Process Control the Right Way, *ASEE Annual Conference*, Seattle, WA.
- Moor, S.S. and Piergiovanni, P.R. (2004) "Inductive Learning in Process Control", Proceedings of the 2004 American Society for Engineering Education Annual Conference & Exposition.
- Edgar, T.F., Ogunnaike, B.A., Downs, J.J., Muske, K.R. and Bequette, W (2006). Renovating the Undergraduate Process Control Course, *Computers and Chemical Engineering*, Vol.30, 2006, pp.1749-1762.
- Felder, R.F. and Brent R (2003). Designing and Teaching Courses to Satisfy the ABET Engineering Criteria, *J. of Engrg. Education*, 92 (1), pp.7-25.
- Cheah, S.M (2009). Integrating CDIO Skills in a Core Chemical Engineering Module: A Case Study, *5th International CDIO Conference*, June 8-10, 2009; Singapore.
- Thomas, C.E (2009). *Process Technology Troubleshooting*, Delmar Cengage Learning.
- Perkins, D. N (1991). Educating for Insight, *Educational Leadership*, 49/2, 1991; pp.4-8